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Native form of Hindi Cinema and lingua franca of Bollywood

Dr. Ajit Kumar Tiwari
Assistant Professor,
Dept. of Hindi,
Rishi Bankim Chandra College
West Bengal State University

There was a time when native form of Hindi Cinema was a matter of greater dispute. There was a common-sense per that Urdu was the representative of Hindi Cinema. Creative presence of lyricists and dialogue writers like Kaifi Azmi, Sahir Ludhianwi, Majruh Sultanpuri, Gulzaar and Javed Akhtar let this perception be a common-sense. At present visible overuse of English is posing the same question before the cine pundits and critics. Javed Akhtar looks concerned about the increasing dominance of English in Hindi Cinema as he said, “Recently English is dominating our Film industry. I am saddened with the treatment of scripts of our recent films.” He figured out two point in which primarily screenplay writers are coming from English background while they don’t have adequate knowledge of Hindi and Urdu. On the other hand, actors are to blame the most because they are nowhere around the literary traditions of Hindi or Urdu. Leave alone Urdu, they can’t even pronounce the Hindi properly. It has direct impact on script writing. Due to these two issues, Javed Akhtar feels that Bollywood lacks Hindi films in adequate Hindi. English is being used even in the screenplays written in common Hindi.

Films of the directors like Imtiaz Ali, Karan Johar, Gouri Shinde, Anurag Basu, Anurag Kashyap and R. Balki are the evidence when we can find the concerns expressed by Javed Akhtar. Dialogues and lyrics used in their films have a range from local dialect to English at the same time. ‘Gangs of Wasseypur part 1 & part 2’ experimented with language at its artistic best. Let’s have a look at a

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song with the mixed language:

‘*Taar Biji se patle* hamaare piya, *as thin as wire* hammare piya’ ...

तार बिजली से पतले हमारे पिया, ऐज थिन ऐज वायर हमारे पिया... and

‘Mera joota *fake leather* dil *chhichhaledar*, wo hamse poochha *whether I want leather* ...’

मेरा जूता फेक लेदर दिल छीछालेदर, वो हमसे पूछा व्हेदर आई बांट लेदर ?

Here, leather is rhymed with ‘chhichhaledar’ (छीछालेदर) that means spoiler. Another song in this film has the lyrics as: ‘*I am a hunter she wanted see my gun, when I pull it out, why the woman started run...*’ However, the same film has songs with adequate lyrics and philosophical meanings. A song written by Piyush Mishra says:

‘Ek bagal mein chand hoga ek bagal mein rotiyan, ek bagal mein neend hogi ek bagal mein siskiyan ...’

एक बगल में चांद होगा, एक बगल में रोटियाँ / एक बगल में नींद होगी, एक बगल में सिसकियां...

Some scripts do prompt a change in basic assumptions that local and global can co-exist in cinemas if you have spontaneity and metal in your content and ‘Gangs of Wasseypur’ is one of them.

A certain genre of Bollywood experimenting with tongue and tone of common people find an advocate in Gulzar. He sounds very clear in his views that if our generation is using a mix and not so pure language so why can’t it be reflected in our cinemas. Isn’t our cinema representing our very society, he asks to purists. Gulzar thinks that language of the cinema remains the same as the people of concerned society behave. Earlier, there was a section who didn’t want Urdu to be mixed with Hindi like now a day’s purist who are uncomfortable with English. Once Sahir Ludhianwi was in Bihar for any Mushayara in the decade of 1960s and stated that language of Hindi cinema is 97 percent Urdu. A magazine named ‘*माधुरी (Madhuri)*, known for journalism related to cinemas, went after Sahir in toto. It published a letter on the page named ‘*चले पवन की चाल*’ (Gone with the

wind). Writer of this letter chose to be anonymous as ‘*फिल्मेश्वर*’ and the letter titled as ‘*हिन्दी और उर्दू के नाम पर नफरत के शोले भड़काने वाले अवसरवादी साहिर के नाम एक खुला पत्रा*’ (An open letter to opportunist Sahir spreading hatred in the name of Hindi and Urdu). This letter is very interesting because it asserts it is Hindi only which Sahir assumed as Urdu just because it’s written in Persian script. It was a classic case of dispute within ‘One language and two scripts’ as Francesca Orsini would suggest.

Be it Sahir, Javed or so called Filmeshwar, everyone has an assumption that the lingua franca used in Hindi cinema has to be uniformalised. Filmeshwar assumes it as Hindi, for Sahir it is Urdu and Javed describes it as a composite form of Hindi/Urdu. At this point Gulzar seems to be more progressive with his idea of a common language. To mitigate the dispute, Hindustani came to rescue. Hindustani term had the essential quality to assimilate both Hindi and Urdu. As for as nationality or native form was concerned, Hindustani had an answer and secularists found it more convenient than purists. However, the question of regional languages/dialects and English was still a matter of concern for the purists. Tradition started from ‘Lagaan’ came to ‘Dangal’ with an idea that local can co-exists with global. ‘Lagaan’ has the diversity of characters ranging from rural to ruler and subalterns to elites.

‘Lagaan’ established the idea of nationality with subaltern perspective and language played a key role. A conversation between Captain Russel and Bhuvan is evident that English is not a spoiler itself. If you have a compact script and metal in your screenplay it can be an icing on the cake. There is a scene when Russel was busy in hunting a deer and at the same time Bhuvan was trying to save that poor chap. Russel says, “*समझा। पाँच बार मैं उस हिरण को क्यों नहीं मार सका। तुम जानवरों के रक्षक हो!*” (Understand why I could not hunt that deer five times. You are an animal saver!) Local soldiers told him, “*किसान है हज़ूर, चंपानेर का!*”(Sir he is a peasant of Champaner.) Russel taunts, “Wow, you must be a very good runner.” And then points his gun at a bunny and says to Bhuvan, “Now try to save this one.” And again, warns Bhuvan, “Next time I will shoot you. *अगली बार*

निशाना तुम्हें बनाऊंगा”. I have mentioned Lagaan because of its lyrics also which are written by none other than Javed Akhtar. Lyrics of Lagaan consists of local dialects, Urdu, Hindi and English altogether. Only two songs of Lagaan like ‘बार-बार हाँ बोलो यार हाँ, अपनी जीत हो उनकी हार हाँ...’ and ‘ओ री छोरी मान भी ले बात मोरी...My heart it speaks a thousand words I feel eternal bliss...’ are evident of the lingua franca that defines the Hindi cinema.

Hindi Cinema has moved on from the old-school debates of its native form and content as for as language is concerned. Now the changing lingua franca of Bollywood is defining the diversity of Hindi language and its dialects. Stories and scripts are being written with subaltern point of view and getting the center stage. Dialectic or Desi tone is the new cool in Hindi Cinema and expressing itself with sense of pride and self-esteem. Films like ‘Lagaan’, ‘Gangs of Wasseypur part 1 & part 2’, ‘Paan Singh Tomar’, ‘Massan’, ‘Nil Batey Sannata’ and recently released ‘Dangal’ are the evidence that dialect is no bar when it comes to the content of a script. Songs and dialogues of these films consists of the tones in which rural India express itself. Tone of local dialects is changing the flavour of Hindi cinema and leaving a great impact. Mahavir Singh Fogat asks in ‘Dangal’ ‘म्हारी छोरियां छोरों से कम हैं के !’ (Are our girls’ inferior to boys?), it applies on the language of Bollywood as well. Lingua franca of Hindi cinema is no less than others and defines the very native form. However, increasing use of English is a major concern that purists think should be addressed properly.